

The Role of Sharjah Radio in Islamic Awareness and Education

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
June 15, 2021

Accepted:
January 22, 2022

Keywords :

Islamic Awareness,
Education, Islamic Law,
Media Planning

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5889051

Abstract

The study aims at the role of Sharjah Radio in instilling awareness and Islamic education in the Emirati society in the midst of regional and international changes. The study reached a number of results, including: Sharjah Radio refines the skills of media professionals and the origins of the media profession and develops its stages by organizing specialized courses in the fields of media planning and strategic thinking. Radio media in community participation contributes to raising awareness of the importance of Islamic education. The study recommended a set of recommendations, including: working on preparing scientific plans in a scientific and strategic way, benefiting from efforts, and building on them, which are in line with the objectives of Sharjah Radio and the objectives of Islamic law, and working to increase religious programs which targets values and customs, and like them to daily life in people's dealings with each other. Here are some, with the support of Islamic awareness and sound Islamic education.

Introduction

Media plays an important role by listening to the audience and listeners in general, and the young demographic in particular, as the technological development of modern communications, has allowed the development of the digital system to be used in radio broadcasting as well as to offer multiple and diverse radio channels whether governmental or private and general or specialized. This development has led to an effective impact on society. Therefore, the issue of instilling values and establishing Islamic awareness among the youth in the Emirati society is one of the issues that represent an important founding source in protecting the youth and building the Islamic cultural character. Thus, it was necessary to address it through the role of Sharjah Radio in instilling and developing Islamic awareness among the youth in the Emirati society, as Islamic awareness and education are considered as special and distinct creation that stems from the Islamic and humanitarian ideology, given its close relation with Islamic history. The world has witnessed many changes, including the use of radio media in raising awareness and concern for Islamic education in society and dealing with Islamic educational values rationally and seriously through categorizing its audience, applying them in real life, and including its role in the economic field as one of the basics of Islamic cultural tourism, in which it plays a great role. We are inspired by Islamic education, specifically by what it contains of innovations in the creative and artistic field. Hence, Islamic values are regarded as the nation's treasure, through which it imposes its existence, proves itself, and maintain its privacy, and in order for our Islamic values and education to remain an essential component of our identity, we seek refuge in them in the midst of modern changes and exotic cultures. It was necessary to use the radio media to instill awareness and Islamic education in society in light of the tremendous technological development and the sweeping trends coming from every direction, which seek to sweep societies, enforce stereotypes, dominate them, culturally alienate them, and influence the emerging generation that we rely on to be the future generation to lead our society.

The Study Problem:

Islamic awareness and education are among the pillars of identity and very important elements, as they present the expressive cultural and living aspect of peoples, groups, and individuals. This was proven, as they acquire that utmost importance always and forever, whether in the present, past, or the future. Islamic awareness and education facilitate culture, knowledge, creativity, civilized values, and the nature of relationships between individuals, who spread cultural awareness. The different time periods also proved the importance of Islamic awareness and education and their great role in preserving the identity of every Islamic society. However, Islamic education today faces in many Islamic countries, especially some Arab countries whose civilization extends to the depths of Islamic history, a set of dangers that threaten its existence and continuity as a witness to Islamic civilization in its various stages. However, it is worth noting that the issue of protecting, paying attention to, and preserving it was not addressed with greater care by introducing Islamic awareness and education through various means in order to preserve it. Therefore, it did not receive much attention from the media, nor was it promoted by the radio media, which constitute the problem. Thus, the study problem lies in the following:

1. What is the role of Sharjah Radio in instilling Islamic awareness and education within society in the United Arab Emirates, at the level of media and social work?
2. What is the real challenge that prevents the radio media (Sharjah Radio) from contributing to raising awareness of the importance of preserving Islamic education in Emirati society?

The Study Objectives:

The study aims mainly to study the role of Sharjah Radio in instilling Islamic awareness and education in Emirati society.

There are some sub-objectives derived from the main objective of the study, which are:

1. Highlighting the challenges and obstacles that radio media faces in general, and Sharjah Radio in particular, that prevent it from effectively playing its role.
2. Knowing the impact of using radio media on community participation and its importance in raising Islamic awareness and education.
3. Assessing the role of radio media and its importance in instilling Islamic awareness and education in the United Arab Emirates and presenting tangible results that contribute to the development of the media system.

The Study Significance:

This significance is demonstrated by:

1. Shedding light on the role of radio in the Emirate of Sharjah in raising awareness and preserving Islamic education in the Emirati society.
2. Assessing the role of Sharjah Radio and its various contributions on the social and cultural level, as well as its attempts and achievements in raising awareness of the importance of preserving Islamic education in Emirati society.
3. Documenting the role of radio media in instilling Islamic awareness and values among the youth by documenting the role of Sharjah Radio as a model in the effective community participation at the local level, as well as paying attention to Islamic values, knowing the obstacles they face and methods to develop their role.

The Study Methodology:

To achieve the study objectives, the descriptive analytical approach was adopted, through which the phenomenon under study, the relationships between its parts, the opinions expressed about it, and the processes and effects resulting from this study, are described.

The Study Plan:

First Chapter: The Emergence and Development of Sharjah Radio.

Second Chapter: Radio Programs, Their Roles, and Their Impact on Society.

Third Chapter: The Role of Sharjah Radio in Islamic Awareness and Education.

First Chapter: The Emergence and Development of Sharjah Radio

Radio is one of the means of mass communication in which the level of communication between the audience is considered limited, because the communication areas or tools do not allow the public to communicate or the large participation that is practiced, for example, in the contemporary media model. Receiving programs from radio stations has been going on for a long time, confined to radio receivers at home, limiting the public's desire to discuss and comment on those programs due to the scarcity of available communication methods and tools, and not only that but most of the programs were recorded programs before the radio was transmitted traditionally to the stage of open space via live broadcast.

Sharjah Broadcasting Authority is a government authority concerned with the development of the media sector in the Emirate of Sharjah. Since the launch of Sharjah TV on February 11, 1989, it has been a natural progression for the expansion of television and radio media work. The development of media institutions in the UAE and their impact on cultural development Sharjah Radio was established in 1971 and debuted on October 10, 1971. At the time of the radio's inception, it broadcast its programs on a wavelength of 190.5 meters and a frequency of 1575 kilocycles, as well as on an FM wave of 98 MHz, and the radio station was located within the Qasimia area, i.e. the location of Sawt Al Sahel radio station.

On January 1, 1976, Sharjah Radio joined the Ministry of Information and Culture, and the station had several studios, including an on-air studio, a program recording studio, and an FM program studio, aside from the news section.

Sharjah Radio's most important programs include (Think and Win Program), (Maeda Al Maarefa), (The Numbers Game), (On Air Clinic), and (Souk Okaz). During the October 1973 war, Sharjah Radio was linked to the Egyptian, Voice of the Arabs "Sawt Al-Arab" channel to transmit military reports issued by Egyptian forces as a solidarity initiative from Sharjah with their brethren in Egypt. Sharjah Radio ceased broadcasting after about three years due to a request from the Federal Government, which wanted to fully supervise the media in the country, and Sharjah Radio resumed broadcasting over the air on November 15, 2000, carrying the message of thought, education, and guidance through its targeted and distinguished programs.

Sharjah Radio is now part of the Sharjah Broadcasting Authority, and the authority has become specialized in the following duties:

- Full supervision of the radio administratively, programmatically, and technically.
- Creating, implementing, and translating radio policy through radio programs and news broadcasts by the radio.

It hosts a number of TV and radio channels, and the centers are: Sharjah TV, Sharjah Sports TV, Sharqiya Kalba TV, Al Wousta Al Dhaid TV, Sharjah 2 TV, Sharjah Radio, Quran Radio from Sharjah, Watar FM, Pulse 95 Radio, Sharjah Media Training Center.

We can review some of the objectives of Sharjah Radio as follows:

- Contribute to the development of national media cadres capable of keeping up with modern development requirements and developments.
- Strengthening the role of the media, particularly in the areas of family formation and interdependence.
- Developing media performance based on professionalism, excellence, creativity, responsible freedom, and adherence to media ethics.
- Preserving the Arab-Islamic heritage through radio programs that reflect this heritage.
- Informing society of the best inventions, contributions, and experiences produced by Islamic culture.
- Contribute to spreading awareness and education among listeners.
- Introducing the United Arab Emirates, its urban renaissance, and its ancient heritage to people from all over the world.

Second Chapter: Radio Programs, Their Roles, and Their Impact on Society

Radio programs and the media, in general, play an important role in the process of socialization, youth development, and instilling stereotypes and roles for both genders, males and females. The majority of the main characters in radio and radio programs are men, while the minor ones are women. However, both genders play an important role in the process of developing the individual and forming his personality, and the media is a psychological and social weapon that can help or harm society, and its goal is to influence the behavior of individuals and groups and direct it according to need, goal, and necessity so that the behavior becomes adapted according to certain standards and criteria.

As a result of communication and media technology, the young demographics exposed to multiple messages, and some of these messages contain many values and behavior patterns that contradict their values, which may have a negative impact on their thought and behavior. Societies that adopt traditional institutions, such as schools, families, and places of worship, tend to have values that are more conservative, stable, and less likely to change. As for societies that depend on institutions of contemporary upbringing, including mass media culture, their value systems tend to change quickly and at any time, and values may conflict in these societies.

Hence, the role that radio programs and the media play in developing and shaping an individual's personality is a delicate pivotal role and a double-edged sword, so it is critical that youth, both male and female, are aware of the problems that the media can cause in an accurate and clear manner so that they are not reflected passive interaction with the media. In this case, the media has a social responsibility to assist these youth in establishing appropriate standards for judging things, as well as to develop in them the ability to think critically and scientifically, in order to test the prevailing values and determine their suitability for the application and use in judging matters.

A variety of programs are produced by radio stations with the aim of attracting listeners' attention, as the radio program is an idea that is processed on the radio, as radio is a means of communication that is primarily based on the audio aspect. Radio programs are constantly evolving and aim to provide first and foremost information, acculturation, education, guidance, direction, entertainment, recreation, and advertising through their various contents and formats. Those in charge of radio programs planning strive to strike a balance between these various objectives. There are several patterns and types of radio programs that radio stations broadcast, including

Directed Programs: This is one of the oldest types of radio programs. This type of program addresses a variety of political, religious, economic, cultural, and social issues, with the aim of influencing listeners in the same way that commercial advertising does.

Talk Shows: They are radio programs in which the method of presentation and dialogue is characterized by simplicity, spontaneity, and improvisation as well as the conversation between its broadcaster and a guest.

Discussions and Debates Programs: They are an extension of the Talk Radio programs, but with special nature. These programs depend on some topics to be discussed or the coverage of a phenomenon that attracted the attention of the audience in order to identify and reach some conclusions. Discussion programs are also characterized by different perspectives, orientations, actions, and attitudes regarding the topic of the discussion, and the difference in points of view between participants may sometimes be turned into a conflict and state of tension.

Entertainment and Variety Programs: These types of shows are considered one of the most widespread radio programs, as they represent key elements of radio media that provide guidance, direction, and education through leisure and entertainment

Specialty Programs: They are dramatic programs with cultural and documentary content, as they talk about a specific person, an event, a concept, a phenomenon, or an idea thoroughly from various aspects, as well as discussing such topics with integrated coverage

Chapter Three

The Role of Sharjah Radio in Islamic Awareness and Education.

Islamic awareness and education are considered among the fundamental elements of the Emirati society due to their great value and influence on the psychological life of individuals, as well as the social life, political alliances, and social cohesiveness. Therefore, they are considered tools for global understanding and a key element to achieving behavioral stability and consistency in society. The psychological impact is also one of the most important factors that affect whether negatively or positively such stability; especially in the midst of the hardships and difficult circumstances we are going through and in light of the Information and communications technology we are witnessing nowadays.

The mass media's role in developing the growing societies has drawn the attention of researchers in the fields of knowledge, whether they are political scientists, sociologists, communication, or economists, especially with the emergence of the modern-day media. Hence, many studies have been conducted in order to find the correlation between mass media and development; as well as to identify the role of mass media and its effectiveness in achieving the development of societies. Since human life is mainly based on the communications between human beings, mass media plays a major role and impacts their lives greatly at the personal and community levels. Radio media is also achieving such an impact by playing an important role in the development of awareness and Islamic education among young people which in turn positively benefits society.

Mass media realizes many cognitive, emotional, and behavioral impacts on the audience. Cognitive impacts are achieved when media provides information and news about the issues that people want to know, while emotional impacts are achieved when media helps people to take actions towards the issues of the society by analyzing information and supporting their developmental attitudes towards such issues as appropriate to their psychological and social needs, while behavioral effects are achieved when media help the audience in how to behave towards differences.

This theory has been interpreted to the extent to which mass and indirect or weak and strong means of communication affect the audience, as it called the environmental theory due to its great interest in the reflection of social relations and its direct connection to the process of mass media influence on the public.

This theory is associated with the effectiveness of the radio stations in the UAE, led by Sharjah Radio, which had been a model to be followed in recent years, as the number of radio stations has increased in UAE, which has affected the traditional model of radio media and the role that radio stations can generally play in the development process of the cognitive, emotional and behavioral needs of the audience and its impact on achieving comprehensive development in the UAE and its future plan to achieve progress and the ability of radio to involve society in the development process.

Conclusion

Finally, the researcher addressed that there are a series of risks in the meantime that threaten the survival and continuity of the Islamic awareness and education as a witness to Islamic civilization in its various stages in many Islamic countries; especially the Arab countries that have a long legacy in the Islamic history. What is the role of Sharjah Radio in instilling awareness and Islamic education in the Emirati society at the levels of media and social work; as the failure of the local radio (Sharjah Radio) to play its role in developing awareness and introducing Islamic education to the audiences will lead to a societal collapse and a breakdown of its moral, scientific and cultural relations, and accordingly the collapse of the country itself with all its institutions as well as walking in a dark tunnel in terms of moral and societal aspects. Therefore, mass media is regarded as a Chinese wall in the face of such risks and suspicious cultural invasion. The study reached a number of results and recommendations based on dividing the research into three chapters. One of these results and recommendations are that Sharjah Radio hosts guides by relying on sermons using the "Dialogue Method" and the question-and-answer approach to arouse the attention of community members and motivate their intelligence; Paying particular attention to presenting the correct and tolerant picture of Islam, and using correct concepts to persuade the youth with contemporary ideas and issues that are not incompatible with the essence of Islamic education in Emirati society.

Study results and recommendations

Through this study, in which the researcher hopes to have managed to identify the various elements and basic concepts associated with the study after analyzing the data he obtained about the study sample in order to clarify

the most important conclusions obtained based on the results of the analysis, in addition to presenting some recommendations, which the researcher believes that it will benefit some specific parties.

First: study results:

1. The study concluded that Sharjah Radio refines the skills of media professionals and the origins of the media profession and develops its stages by organizing specialized courses in the fields of media planning and strategic thinking.
2. Sharjah Radio always strives to provide a legal environment that guarantees freedom of the media and that determines the nature of the relationship between it and the executive institutions.
3. Sharjah Radio is keen to contribute to the consolidation of the individual behaviors and the prevalence of the individual's whims and emotions as well as imposes objective media standards.
4. The study has reached that there is a weakness in the extent to which media professionals in Sharjah Radio acquire a general culture.
5. Sharjah Radio is keeping pace with the developments of modernization in the new media and communication technology; as well as understanding all the updates that occur in the media field and landscape.
6. Sharjah Radio hosts guides by relying on sermons using the "Dialogue Method" and the question-and-answer approach to arouse the attention of community members and motivate their intelligence.
7. Sharjah Radio produces daily programs that aim to provide guidance, instill awareness, encourage the youth to turn away from committing sins and promote Islamic education.
8. Sharjah Radio is keen, through its programs, to develop self-awareness within educational programs to enhance the cultural, social, and Islamic awareness desired to be achieved.
9. Radio media in community participation contributes to raising awareness of the importance of Islamic education.

Study recommendations:

According to the results and conclusions reached by the researcher and in order for this study to play its role and achieve its objectives in the best possible way; Some recommendations must be made, which are as follows:

1. Working on preparing scientific plans in a scientific and strategic way, benefiting from efforts, and building on them, which are in line with the Objectives of Sharjah Radio and the objectives of Islamic law.
2. Increasing and developing the content of the specialized programs that related to human development issues presented by Sharjah Radio as well as working on developing the same and striving to provide new and meaningful information.
3. Working on the content of the programs and presenting the same in a simplified way to make it easier to understand and solve the problems of society, as well as involving the local community in proposing the possible solutions for such problems.
4. Monitoring the real reactions of the audience as well as working to increase communication between the people of the community and the radio.
5. Paying attention to different segments of the society in the religious programs presented by the Sharjah Radio.
6. Working to increase religious programs which target values and customs, and link them to daily life in people's dealings with each other, in a way that supports Islamic awareness and sound and proper Islamic education.
7. Paying particular attention to presenting the correct and tolerant picture of Islam, and using correct concepts to persuade the youth with contemporary ideas and issues that are not incompatible with the essence of Islamic education in Emirati society.

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